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Technological innovation for resilience and sustainability: insights from the energy-intensive ecosystem

Abstract. This study investigates how technological innovation can foster both supply chain sustainability and transformative resilience, focusing on the European energy-intensive ecosystem. Through multiple case analyses, the research identifies key technology-driven actions implemented at different levels by a set of steel and metal companies to enhance their sustainability and resilience, such as heat recovery systems and waste recycling initiatives. Collaboration emerges as a fundamental enabler across all levels of the supply chain, highlighting the importance of cross-sector cooperation. The findings highlight the interconnectedness of technological innovation, collaboration, and learning as key enabling capabilities in driving the supply chain transformation.

Keywords: supply chain resilience, sustainability, technological innovation.

1 Introduction

In the past years, the focus of supply chain sustainability research has been mainly devoted to reducing environmental risks. Parallely, literature on supply chain (SC) resilience has mainly addressed how to face disruptions. Several authors have started to analyse resilience and sustainability through a social-ecological lens investigating the interplay of sustainability with resilience in supply chains [1, 2]. Among SC resilience approaches, the authors investigated how supply chains transform their processes to be resilient and achieve long-term sustainability.

In this context, technology could play a great role. Looking at the European context, the transformative impact of a digital, data-driven and interconnected industry was grounded on the implementation of Industry 4.0 as a guiding principle for the innovation and technological development of the European supply chains. Focusing on the operational field, supply chains need to leverage and exploit the opportunities offered by an approach where technological innovation converges for transforming society and the business-centric vision broadens towards a society-centric vision.

Analysing transformation enabled by technologies to face major external risks, the paper aims to investigate how technological innovation can lead supply chains to sustainability and transformative resilience.

2 Research background

2.1 Supply chain resilience and sustainability

The literature reveals that most of the research focuses on a specific sustainability model, e.g., circular economy, or a specific dimension of sustainability, e.g., environmental or social, rather than approaching resilience and sustainability in a more comprehensive way. However, some authors are currently investigating it by adopting a social-ecological approach to studying resilience and sustainability. Silva et al. [2] assume that resilience and sustainability are dance partners that influence each other by learning and thus, transforming supply chains. Transformation in resilience research dates to Wieland [3] who provided a new social-ecological transformative perspective in analysing resilience. Following this approach, supply chains are guided to move to a new normality after a disruption. From the analysis of this approach to build SC resilience and sustainability, the following capabilities are recognized to enable transformation i.e., collaboration and learning. Collaboration has been investigated as a capability either for resilience by analysing the collaboration practices which support the development of resilience, such as information sharing, collaborative communication, resource sharing, etc. [4] or for sustainability [5]. Moving to a new normality, i.e. transformation, means to collaborate in new ways with usual SC partners and by creating new forms of collaboration with other actors in the ecosystems beyond the traditional SC boundaries [1, 6]. This allows SCs to develop resilience [4] and sustainability [7]. Finally, after a disruption, learning from experience plays an essential role in the development of resilience and moving to long-term sustainability [1]. Learning means creating and sharing knowledge within the firm, transferring and sharing knowledge across the sector and the broader supply chain, and exchanging and sharing knowledge with the wider ecosystem [6].

2.2 Technological innovation for resilience and sustainability

SC sustainability and resilience highly depend on digitalizing the respective processes to increase performance and transform the way to do business [8]. While the **Internet of Things (IoT)** increases transparency [9] enabling data collection throughout the supply chain and better decision-making [10], **Blockchain** supports a decentralized, secure, and transparent digital ledger, allowing end-to-end traceability of products and smart contracts [11]. **Artificial Intelligence** applications enhance risk identification, disruption early detection, countermeasure initiation and improved decision-making in different SC tasks [12]. **Digital twins** allow the creation of virtual SC models to test and predict the effect of different actions in different simulated scenarios [13]. **Supply chain sustainability platforms** help companies to improve sustainability in

cooperation with SC actors through a shared approach to measuring and managing ecological and social goals [14]. The specific character of the steel and metal sector relates to the increasing concentration of current technologies on **hydrogen** and **heat recovery systems** as well as the treatment of slag and by-products. Hydrogen is used as a cleaner alternative to traditional coal-based methods to reduce carbon emissions and produce green steel [15]. Heat recovery systems are implemented to capture and reuse waste heat from the steelmaking process, enhancing energy efficiency and further contributing to sustainability efforts in the sector.

2.3 Energy intensive ecosystems

Within the energy-intensive ecosystem outlined by the EU Commission, the steel sector is a key component that makes up a significant part of the European industrial and economic landscape. This ecosystem, which also includes the chemical, paper and mining industries, is essential for the supply of intermediate products in various sectors and works closely with the energy, waste and recycling industries [16]. The steel industry, a cornerstone of this network, not only generated a turnover of 125 billion euros in 2021 but also employed 310,000 people and produced 153 million tons of steel annually [16]. The production of this sector underlines its crucial role in supporting almost 2.5 million indirect jobs and underlines its essential contribution to the EU's industrial framework and economy [16, 17].

This ecosystem faces challenges in green and digital transitions, necessitating investments in innovations such as hydrogen-based steel production and carbon capture to reduce environmental impacts [18]. With these industries consuming nearly 70% of the EU's energy, balancing global market dynamics and fixed international pricing complicates maintaining competitiveness while achieving the EU's environmental and digital goals [16].

3 Methodology

A purposeful sampling method was used and accordingly, three companies operating at different SC levels that are representative in terms of innovative practices for sustainable procurement, production and distribution in the steel and metal value chain were selected. Each company has already in place a strategy that also involves their SC, to innovate business through investment, training, and technologies to support enhanced sustainability and resilience.

The data collection employed both primary and secondary sources. Secondary data have been used to get familiar with the companies, their sustainability practices and SC. In each case, in-depth interviews were conducted with managers who have a significant understanding of the risks faced in the sustainability path (i.e. CEOs, CTOs, sustainability managers, R&D and operations managers) at the SC level. In most cases, multiple respondents and investigators were involved in the interview meetings to enhance the validity and reliability of the collected data [19].

The information collected was then integrated with secondary information from further company documentation, aiming at triangulation purposes for consistency of findings and mitigation of bias [19]. The interviews were conducted between October 2023 and January 2024. In this period, the researchers interactively performed data collection and analysis to review and refine the emerging findings.

As a first step, open coding was used to understand the empirical findings and their relation to the research objectives [20]. To develop the analysis, we focused on understanding the type of actions developed to face sustainability risks for each case studied in terms of technologies used, type of collaboration and learning. This process led to the development of first-order codes that ended up in a table (Table 1) used to support the within-case analysis and to start the cross-analysis based on all the actions. The results were compared with the extant literature to ensure theory elaboration. Therefore, emerging characteristics related to sustainability and resilience have been explored to investigate how actions leverage the identified dimensions for transformation. Additionally, to achieve dependability and confirmability, multiple researchers added interpretation to the data.

4 Findings

Based on the interviews and other information collected, it was possible to formalise the most important actions for sustainability implemented by the companies. Company A is a leader in producing steel for the mechanical, energy and construction industries with electric arc furnaces, where the most critical material is steel scrap (representing 95% of the total raw material). The increasing costs of raw materials and energy prices of the last years shed light on two main challenges for the Company, i.e. heat and water dispersion respectively from exhaust steam and cooling process and high amount of metallic waste landfilled (in terms of slag). Within this context, the company adopted two actions. A **heat recovery system (A1)** enables the large amount of heat in the fumes of the electric arc furnace to be conveyed into a system that avoids its dispersion. The heat is recovered and used for a dual purpose: as thermal energy fed into the municipality heating network and as electricity for internal use. The company is implementing **industrial symbiosis (A2)**, reusing metallic waste rich in iron oxide generated by production cycles, and reducing the quantity of material going to landfills. Metallic waste is collected from different actors, processed using advanced technology and transformed into a secondary raw material for recovery or reuse through a set of innovative units (pyrolysis plant, SiO₂ separation, reducing furnace, briquetting and char injector).

Company B is a retail company distributing steel products. It prioritizes high-quality materials and innovation, aiming for efficient and ethical supply chains, primarily in Europe. The company focuses on sustainability but struggles with truck transportation emissions, energy consumption in storage/processing, and compliance with the Supply Chain Protection Act to uphold standards. To achieve CO₂ neutrality by 2030, the company is shifting towards more **efficient transportation (B1)** methods, such as rail and shipping, and optimizing transport volumes in collaboration with customers to

reduce emissions and costs. It is also investing in an intelligent energy management system, **green energy (B2)**, and modernizing lighting in warehouses to cut down on energy use. In response to the Supply Chain Law, the firm is enhancing supply chain sustainability by sourcing **certified green materials (B3)** and implementing cloud-based tracking for transparency.

Company C is a German-based company specializing in the production of cold-rolled steel strips. The company offers a diverse product range to industries such as automotive, construction, and precision engineering. Primarily serving the domestic market, it holds a significant position in the European market as well. Despite facing challenges like raw material fluctuations and global market dynamics, the company has maintained its competitive edge through strategic supply chain management and a focus on sustainability. To further this commitment, the company is implementing a transition of the annealing process from gas to **hydrogen (C1)**, aiming for CO₂ neutrality by 2030. Additionally, the company plans to equip systems with meters for **eco-impact tracking (C2)** and display each product's CO₂ footprint in real time, enhancing customer engagement and market presence through transparent and sustainable marketing.

For the cross-case analysis, the case companies are explored through the actions they set, focusing on the role of technological innovation as an enabler for collaboration, and learning. This examination stems from the understanding that these capabilities are fundamental in enabling transformation towards resilience and sustainability. By analysing these key dimensions comparatively across the actions implemented by a steel manufacturing company (Company A), a retail steel company (Company B), and an upstream entity specializing in cold rolling (Company C), the study aims to uncover underlying patterns, strategies, and outcomes that contribute to the organizational success and resilience.

Table 1. Cross-case analysis

Actions	ENABLER	CAPABILITIES	
	Technological innovation	Collaboration	Learning
A1 Heat recovery	Distributed energy generation system and cloud-based platform for energy management	Agreement with energy provider and local municipality for heating provision	Transferability to ecosystems where waste heat from water or gas can be recovered
A2 Waste recycling	Virtual Assessment Platform for enhanced symbiosis activity management	Partnerships with steel and metal companies for recovering steel waste	Transferability to all steel plants, involving SC and external partners from the mechanical sector
B1 Efficient Transport	Logistics optimization tool	Supplier and customer partnership for coordinated delivery dates	Delivery consolidation and maximizing loads

B2 Green Energy	Intelligent energy management system	Development of an energy network with an energy supplier	Green tech expansion limited by site structure and regulations
B3 Certified green steel	Cloud-based tracking solution	Data sharing with suppliers, providing data to customers	Challenges in SC law compliance: secrecy and monitoring limits of smaller companies
C1 Hydrogen	New annealing technologies (hydrogen /electricity)	Choosing and developing new technology with experts and provider	Development of awareness on the potential and economic viability of green hydrogen
C2 Eco-Impact Tracking	Metering system	Data sharing with suppliers, providing data to customers	Enhancement of customer and market awareness of product sustainability

5 Discussion and conclusions

As can be noted in Fig. 1, most of the actions on sustainability need to involve many actors beyond the supply chain borders. While Efficient Transportation (B1) is mainly devoted to supply chain relationship improvement, the implementation of Hydrogen technologies (C1) and Waste Recycling (A2) need to enlarge the collaboration by adding new tiers to the supply chain respectively with technology providers and treatment centres. Green Steel (B3) and Eco Impact Tracking (C2) need to create a straight and trusty collaboration with 2nd and 3rd tier suppliers that need to give access to information about their processes. The most transformative actions are related to Heat Recovery (A1) and Green Energy (B2) where it is necessary to enlarge to other stakeholders like municipalities and consumer associations as well as energy providers.

Fig. 1. The actions for resilience and sustainability according to their level of integration with SC, ecosystem or enlarged ecosystem.

This paper provides some preliminary theoretical and managerial implications showing how actions driven by technological innovation can help transformation.

In particular, some actions (like A1, B2 and A2) are transforming the ecosystem thanks to new partnerships with companies (including competitors) operating in the same districts and creating industrial symbiosis or enlarged ecosystem actors like public entities [21]. The learning process is leveraged on the transferability of these best practices to the whole companies belonging to the steel ecosystem by replicability process (A1, A2). The study of other actions like C1 helps to increase awareness of the potential and viability of technologies like green hydrogen, to reduce the problem of critical dependencies from energy providers. The reinforcement of the relationship with the 2nd and 3rd tier suppliers like in B3 and C2 facilitates the ecosystem to be more resilient thanks to visibility and traceability of the processes.

Further research can help to generalise these findings involving also other companies of the energy-intensive ecosystem both with new multiple case analysis and later with a large survey to confirm the findings. Moreover, it is necessary to conceptualise new organisational models where businesses collaborate with public entities to increase the social acceptance and sustainability of such type of production with a high impact on energy consumption. The advancement in a sector like steel can have an impact on many other industries in the downstream processes.

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